

Dive Medicine

Module 5 Assessment

Assessment Information

Assessment for this module is made up of several components. An overall mark will be given for tasks completed. Understanding is more important than mathematical precision so it will be to your advantage to describe how you have approached a physics problem even if the final answer is incorrect. Consideration is also given to posts (discussions / ideas / information) made to the forum regarding each task.

Component of Assessment	Available % of total mark
Tasks – Marks will be upon:	
The completion of the tasks	15%
The extent of knowledge and understanding demonstrated	15%
Tasks for papers 1 to 6 can be found following this table	
Paper 1 – Marks will be based upon the extent of knowledge and understanding demonstrated	5%
Paper 2 - Marks will be based upon the extent of knowledge and understanding demonstrated	5%
Paper 3 - Marks will be based upon the extent of knowledge and understanding demonstrated	10%
Paper 4 - Marks will be based upon the extent of knowledge and understanding demonstrated	5%
Paper 5 - Marks will be based upon the extent of knowledge and understanding demonstrated	5%
Paper 6 – Marks will be based upon: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The extent of knowledge and understanding demonstrated • Correct identification of appropriate differential diagnoses • Correct identification of additional information required (medical and other) to make a final diagnosis • Correct identification of the most likely diagnosis/diagnoses • Appropriate management: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ with a recompression chamber on-site ○ with no chamber available ○ with a chamber one or two hours away 	15%
Forum – Marks will be based upon: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Amount of input to the forum • The extent of knowledge and understanding demonstrated by the input 	5%
Online Multiple Choice Questions	20%
Total	100%

Paper 1

Write short notes describing what factors you would take into account when assessing fitness to dive in order to reduce the risk of diving accidents. This paper should not be simply a list of items to assess during a medical examination and / or a list of disqualifying conditions. It should describe the principles and supporting evidence (if any exists) behind these in order to demonstrate that you understand how and why particular decisions are made.

Guideline 500 words.

Paper 2

Write short notes describing what factors you would take into account when assessing the diving environment in order to reduce the risk of diving accidents. This paper should not be a simple list of items to assess. It should describe the principles and supporting evidence (if any exists) behind these in order to demonstrate that you understand how and why particular aspects are checked and the measures that can be put in place to improve safety.

Guideline 500 words.

Paper 3

Write short notes describing how you would assess and plan medical support for diving in a remote location where there is no chamber accessible within a reasonable timeframe. This paper should not be a simple list of items to assess and to put into place. It should describe the principles and supporting evidence (if any exists) behind these to demonstrate that you understand why particular facilities and services should be made available to the diving operation. You do not need to repeat material from Papers 1 and 2 although you might need to make reference to it for completeness.

Guideline 1000 words

Paper 4

Write short notes describing how your assessment and planning would differ if there was a recompression chamber within an hour or so evacuation time.

Guideline 500 words.

Paper 5

Write short notes describing how your assessment and planning would differ if there was a recompression chamber on-site.

Guideline 500 words.

Paper 6

Write short notes on the diagnosis and management of the cases described below.

Guideline 100 words per case.

Case 1

A 26 year old recreational diver using a closed-circuit set took 6 breaths from his equipment at the surface before diving and fell unconscious. When his mask and mouthpiece were removed he was tachycardic, tachypnoeic and pale. He made a rapid recovery.

Case 2

A 37 year old scallop diver was working hard at 35 msw on open-circuit SCUBA. His breathing rate was increasing, he developed a throbbing headache and his heart started pounding. He returned to the surface and removed his demand valve. His buddy commented that his face was red. He was tachycardic and tachypnoeic. His headache persisted but the other symptoms resolved spontaneously over the next 5 minutes.

Case 3

A 24 year old surface supplied compressed air diver spends 28 minutes at 43 msw. He ascends, completing all stops. 15 minutes after ascent he complains of a dull pain in his left knee and starts to limp. A quick examination reveals weakness in his left hip and knee, reduced light-touch and pin-prick sensation over left quadriceps. He is taken to a recompression chamber, by which time he has weakness and numbness in the whole of his left leg, weakness in this right knee and numbness over his right calf and shin.

Case 4

A 36 year old recreational diver uses a semi-closed nitrox set for a dive to 52 msw on a wreck. He swims along the long axis of the wreck working against a moderate current. After 15 minutes he feels uncomfortable, has difficulty catching his breath, notices tingling in his fingers and develops tunnel vision. He stops exploring the wreck and begins his ascent. He is recovered unconscious on the surface, he does not remember anything from leaving the bottom to the first few minutes after being recovered into the dive boat and he has urinated in his dry-suit. He complains of pleuritic retrosternal pain and has haemoptysis. His voice has changed.

Case 5

A 26 year old trainee SCUBA diver begins a dive breathing compressed air. He has difficulty descending and makes several forceful valsalva efforts in order to clear his ears. He eventually reaches 28 msw but, after 15 minutes at depth, he begins to feel unsteady. He heads for the surface at the correct rate, observes his safety stop but his symptoms progressively worsen. On the dive boat he has vertigo, he is unable to walk and reports deafness in his right ear.

Case 6

A 29 year old recreational instructor is using a semi-closed circuit oxy-nitrogen set. He descends to 33 msw. After 21 minutes of finning against a strong current he begins his ascent at the correct rate, observing all stops as advised by computer. His buddy notices that he loses consciousness at 3 msw, and ensures that he keeps his mask on and mouthpiece in as he recovers him to the dive boat. The casualty slowly recovers consciousness. He feels well but has no recollection of the last 6 metres of his ascent.

Case 7

A 37 year old breath-hold diver takes a deep breath and descends to 17 msw. He swims along the sea-bed for 5 minutes, gathering coral. A colleague notices that he stops moving and recovers him to shore. He has a pulse but is not breathing. His colleague administers two rescue inflations. The casualty begins to breathe, coughs up a small amount of water and slowly recovers consciousness. He makes a full neurological recovery but, 3 hours later, he develops shortness of breath and pyrexia.

Case 8

A 24 year old surface supplied compressed air diver trainee descends to 48 msw. He reports that he has reached the bottom and feels well. The supervisor makes a weak joke over the communications and the diver laughs uncontrollably, then reports that he can hear a strange whining noise and comments that the fish aren't happy with the quality of his work. The supervisor brings the diver back to the surface where he feels completely well but has left a selection of tools at the seabed and cannot remember the joke or precisely what he has done underwater.

Case 9

A 17 year old recreational student is at 3 m in a swimming pool using compressed air SCUBA. After 2 minutes in the water he begins mask-clearing practice. He inhales water through his nose, panics and swims for the surface. Almost immediately he reaches the poolside he develops tingling and weakness in his left hand and leg. He is given oxygen at the scene while waiting for an ambulance. The weakness improves slightly but the numbness persists. When describing his symptoms he notices that he is having difficulty selecting the correct words.

Case 10

A 64 year old technical diver goes to Scapa Flow for a week of diving. He uses enhanced oxygen nitrox for every dive, high fraction oxygen mixtures for decompression and follows profiles generated by an air computer. Despite this, on the evening of day 5 he develops pain in his right elbow with tingling in the ulnar border of his right forearm, extending into his little finger.

Case 11

A 24 year old diver decides to replace his ageing wet suit and buys a dry-suit. He descends to 24 msw and swims around to try out his new suit. He notices that he is reasonably warm, that the suit feels very snug but that mobility is more restricted and that considerably more effort is required to swim compared with his old wetsuit. He returns to the surface after 10 minutes at the bottom. While he is changing his friend points out a number of blue-red marks over his torso. Now a little more reflective, he notices that the markings are a slightly painful.

Case 12

A 45 year old student diver undertakes her seventh ever dive in a wetsuit, using compressed air SCUBA. She feels slightly cold but not too uncomfortable. She does not exceed 3 msw depth throughout. After 35 minutes of swimming, she feels short of breath at depth, so surfaces and leaves the water. The instructor notices that she is tachypnoeic and slightly cyanosed. She complains of a cough and notices a small fleck of blood in her sputum, although she is sure that she had no problems with her sinuses or ears at any time.

Case 13

A 25 year old technical diver makes a dive to 38 msw. He has 2 cylinders of 30% nitrox & 1 cylinder of 80% nitrox for decompression, each with a separate demand valve. He descends breathing the 30% mixture. His demand valve starts to malfunction after 25 minutes so he changes over to another. Within minutes his buddy sees him convulsing and the demand valve has fallen out of the casualty's mouth by the time he reaches him. The buddy inflates the casualty's buoyancy compensation device to send him to surface. He is found at the surface and flown by helicopter to hospital. In the emergency department the casualty has recovered consciousness but complains of breathlessness and weakness and tingling in both legs. On examination he is tachypnoeic, tachycardic, distressed and has poor cerebation. He has reduced power and sensation in the limbs, crackles throughout his chest and is desaturated on 100% oxygen. His chest x-ray is normal.

Case 14

A 23 year old surface supplied diver completes a 5 minute task at 28 msw. He ascends towards the surface. At 5 msw he experiences sudden pain to the left of his nose and loses the supero-temporal field of vision in his left eye. Within seconds of surfacing he has an epistaxis from his left nostril and the pain gradually settles. His field of vision gradually returns to normal over the next 3 minutes.

Case 15

A 38 year old saturation diver completes a bell run and returns to storage depth at 160 msw. He is completely well when he goes to sleep in the living chamber. He wakes some 6 hours after the end of the bell run and, when he sits up, notices a severe pain in the L4 dermatome with weakness and numbness in his left leg.

Assessment Deadlines

Assessment deadlines can be found in the "Important Dates" document.